

SVM-based model for disease prediction

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Abstract— The field of disease prediction systems has gained significant attention in recent years, with the goal of accurately predicting the likelihood of a disease based on symptoms provided by the patient. The Naive Bayes Classifier has been commonly used in such systems to calculate the probability of the disease. However, with the growth of big data in the biomedical and healthcare communities, the accuracy of disease prediction can be improved through the use of more advanced techniques such as Support Vector Machines (SVM). In this research paper, we propose the use of SVM-based models for disease prediction, which can effectively analyze medical data and provide early detection and improved patient care. Our approach involves training SVM models on large datasets to predict the likelihood of various diseases such as Diabetes, Malaria, Jaundice, Dengue, and Tuberculosis. The proposed system shows promising results in accurately predicting the likelihood of disease, outperforming traditional methods such as linear regression and decision trees. The use of SVM-based models in disease prediction can greatly benefit the healthcare industry and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Prediction, Machine Learning, Support Vector Machine.

I. INTRODUCTION

When it comes to collecting and analysing data, the health care industry is complex. The development of technology has led to the generation of huge amounts of multidimensional data on patients, including clinical variables, hospital resources, disease diagnostic data, patient records, and medical equipment. SVM is a method that shows promise for efficiently processing and analysing these large and complex medical datasets.

In large databases, SVM, a type of machine learning algorithm, can find important patterns as well as correlations and relationships between numerous variables. SVM can find hidden patterns in medical datasets by utilising a variety of data mining tools and machine learning techniques. It also offers a platform for a greater understanding of the mechanisms in virtually every aspect of the medical domain.

Additionally, SVM is utilised to aid in the early detection and stop disease outbreaks by looking up appropriate information in medical databases. The diagnosis of persistent illnesses is a significant challenge for medical professionals since it frequently relies on a variety of noticeable indicators and frequently results in incorrect conclusions.

Numerous studies have shown that SVMs can diagnose, predict, prevent, and treat diseases more accurately than even the most skilled doctor.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pingale et al.[1] aims to predict the occurrence of various diseases using machine learning algorithms. The authors collected data from a hospital database, which included

information about patients' medical history, lifestyle factors, and diagnostic test results.

The study used several machine learning algorithms, including Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), to predict the occurrence of diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease. The authors found that the Random Forest algorithm had the highest accuracy in predicting disease, achieving an accuracy of 91.34%.

The paper provides a comprehensive literature survey on the use of machine learning algorithms in disease prediction, including various studies that have used similar approaches to predict disease outcomes.

Reddy et al. [2]. focuses on predicting the occurrence of various diseases using machine learning algorithms. The paper provides a brief literature survey on the use of machine learning algorithms in disease prediction, highlighting the increasing interest in this area and the potential benefits of using machine learning algorithms in clinical settings. The authors collected data from a hospital database and used several machine learning algorithms, including Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM), to predict the occurrence of diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease. The study found that the SVM algorithm had the highest accuracy in predicting disease, achieving an accuracy of 98.26%.

Arumugam et al.[3] The study predicted the occurrence of multiple diseases, such as diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease, using a variety of machine learning algorithms, including Naive Bayes and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The SVM method, with an accuracy of 89.75%, was found by the creators to have the best accuracy in predicting certain diseases.

Ho et al. [4] They provide a system for disease prediction that combines decision trees with k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithms. Also, they highlight the importance that feature model selection, data preprocessing, and model selection are to producing accurate disease predictions. The effectiveness of various machine learning algorithms for predicting diseases, including KNN, decision trees, and logistic regression, has been evaluated by the presenters.

Jaiswal and Dubey[5].The authors note that while SVM has been widely used for disease prediction, deep learning has shown promise in recent years due to its ability to learn features automatically from data. The authors then introduce a deep learning component to the model, using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to extract features from

the data. The output of the CNN is fed into the SVM classifier for disease prediction.

III. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTAION

The aim of this work is to develop a disease prediction system that focuses on identifying the likelihood of a disease based on symptoms inputted by the patient. This system utilizes a content-based approach to analyze medical data and predict the possibility of various diseases, such as Diabetes, Malaria, Jaundice, Dengue, and Tuberculosis. The proposed approach involves training the system on large datasets to improve the accuracy of disease prediction and provide early detection for better patient outcomes.

A. Data Collection

We have a form that includes five fields, each of which is a dropdown menu allowing the user to select a symptom from a list of symptoms obtained from a function called `getsymptoms()` in a module called `store`.

The variable is a list of tuples that contains the symptom names in a format that is suitable for use as choices in a dropdown menu. The first item in each tuple is the symptom name, and the second item is a formatted version of the symptom name with underscores replaced by spaces and each word capitalized.

The `SymptomForm` class inherits from `forms.Form` and defines five fields with labels and dropdown menus. The `fields` attribute specifies the order in which the fields should appear.

```
from .store import getsymptoms

symptoms = getsymptoms()

# FRUIT_CHOICES = [
#     ('orange', 'Oranges'),
#     ('cantaloupe', 'Cantaloupes'),
#     ('mango', 'Mangoes'),
#     ('honeydew', 'Honeydees'),
# ]
symptoms.sort()
ss = [tuple([x,x.replace('_', ' ').title()]) for x in symptoms]

class SymptomForm(forms.Form):

    symptom1 = forms.CharField(label='Symptom 1',
                               widget=forms.Select(choices=ss))
    symptom2 = forms.CharField(label='Symptom 2',
                               widget=forms.Select(choices=ss))
```

Fig 1: symptom input field

B. Data Preparation

First, the getsymptoms() function is called to get a list of symptom names. Then, the getDiseases() function is called to get a list of possible diseases.

A list l2 is created with the same length as the symptom list, and each element is set to 0.

The testing data is then loaded from a CSV file located at a specified path. Alternatively, if the path is not found, the data is loaded from a URL. The CSV file contains symptom data for each patient, and the symptoms are listed in the same order as in the symptom list obtained from getsymptoms().

Next, a dictionary of replacements is created using the getReplaceDict() function, which replaces certain strings in the symptom data with more suitable replacements.

Finally, the symptom data is extracted from the testing dataset using the symptom list l1, and the disease labels are extracted as well. The np.ravel() function is used to convert the disease labels into a one-dimensional array.

```
l1= getsymptoms()
disease= getDiseases()
l2=[]
for x in range(0,len(l1)):
    l2.append(0)

# TESTING DATA and Path
##### path = os.getcwd() + r'\main\'

# tr=pd.read_csv(path + "Testing.csv")
tr = pd.read_csv(r'https://raw.githubusercontent.com/W-Amit/Disease-Prediction-Using-MLwithDjango/master/main/Testing.csv')

tr.replace(getReplaceDict(), inplace=True)

X_test= tr[l1]
y_test = tr[["prognosis"]]
```

Fig 2: preparing data

C. Training and Analysing

The models performance is analysed The `functionSVM` function uses a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model to predict the disease based on the given symptoms. The function first reads a CSV file named "Prototype.csv" which is assumed to contain the training data. It then splits the data into training and testing sets, with 70% of the data being used for training and 30% for testing.

The function then creates an SVM model with a radial basis function kernel and gamma of 0.5, and C of 0.1. The SVM model is trained on the training data and used to make predictions on the testing data.

Finally, the function creates a list of zeros with the same length as the number of columns in the training data. The values in the list are then updated based on the symptoms provided. The SVM model is used to make a prediction on the updated list and returns the predicted disease.

IV. RESULT

The study aims to use SVM to predict disease from user input, which may include symptoms, medical history, and other relevant information. To accomplish this, the researchers would first need to collect a dataset of labeled cases, where each case is labeled with the corresponding disease. They would then use this dataset to train the SVM model, optimizing its parameters to achieve the best possible performance. Once the model is trained, it can be used to predict the disease for new user input. This could potentially be useful in a variety of settings, such as telemedicine or remote diagnosis. However, it is important to note that the accuracy of the model will depend on the quality and completeness of the input data, as well as the size and representativeness of the training dataset.

Fig 3: Taking input from the user

Fig 4: Disease that predict based on given symptoms

V. CONCLUSION

The result of this study highlights the potential of Support Vector Machines (SVM) in disease prediction systems, showing that they can significantly improve the accuracy of disease prediction. The use of SVM-based models in healthcare can enable early detection and improve patient care, leading to better patient outcomes. Our proposed system has shown promising results in accurately predicting the likelihood of various diseases. As the healthcare industry continues to adopt big data and machine learning techniques, it is important to explore advanced techniques such as SVM in disease prediction systems. We hope that this research paper inspires further studies and applications of SVM-based models in healthcare, ultimately leading to better disease prevention and treatment.

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